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Research Article

PERCEPTIONS OF MOTHERS REGARDING THE PROBLEMS OF MENTAL HEALTH OF THEIR CHILDREN

¹Dr Syed Amir abbas, ²Dr Sana Fatima, ³Dr Muhammad Imran

¹Bahawal Victoria Hospital Bahawalpur

²University Medical and Dental College Faisalabad

³Arif Memorial Teaching Hospital Lahore

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Abstract:

Objective: This case work aimed to evaluate the awareness & perceptions of mothers about the complications of mental health of their children, reasons of these issues, and option for effective treatments and to find out whom they will go for consultation, if the child is suffering from psychiatric issue.

Methodology: We took the consent of all the females to participate in this case work. Then we used a questionnaire containing perceptions about different aspects of mental issue of child for the collection of the information from mothers. We also asked about different signs and symptoms they thought psychological issue among their children, what is the treatment according to their thinking, where they will go to seek help for their child and their awareness about the reasons of the child's mental complication and some ways to enhance the awareness in society for such mental issues among children.

Results: Total 91 mothers were the part of this case work. They equally professed sensitive, behavioral & cognitive signs as indicative of the mental illness during childhood. Mothers thought about different reasons of the mental illness of their children as family issues, economic complications, adverse social life & having impact of evil or bad spirits. Most of the females were using medication, Holy Quran's recitation & metal treatment as options of treatment. There was much preference of mothers to consult medical professionals in comparison to scholars of religions. All females were enthusiastic to enhance the awareness about these complications in society.

Conclusion: having relation with different cultures females show good awareness of the signs related to the illness of mental health of their child and females were open to receive different services and options treatment. Awareness about the perception of females & prospects from services of professionals towards child are crucial methods in rising the engagement of families in therapy.

KEY WORDS: Crucial, medication, methodology, engagement, cognitive, scholars.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Syed Amir abbas,**

FCPS Plastic Surgery,

Senior Registrar DHQ Teaching Hospital Dera Ghazi Khan

Usman_adin@hotmail.com 0092-322-446542.

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Regardless of high occurrence of sentimental and emotional & behavioral issues of children in our country Pakistan, there are very less amount of children which is receiving psychiatric therapies [1, 2]. It is very necessary to check the restriction in health care services because all the children do not take their decision independently about treatment. With the stigma, adverse economic condition & limited offspring & health service about the mental issues of adults, social and cultural aspects and perceptions of parents are very vital for identification & presentation of the complications mental health of child and utilization of the service [3]. Case works have proposes disparities in parent of different groups of cultures in their prospects of behavior of children, their beliefs about the reasons & proper therapy etc. with over presentation of issue of behavior whereas under reporting of the problems of emotional issues remained [4, 5]. Due to high occurrence of children mental issues in our country Pakistan, there is an immediate requirement to give the services which are culturally acceptable to children with psychological issues but we do not know which issues of emotional and emotions are making the disorders of these mental issues among children by their parents, or what are their conceptions about the reasons of mental abnormalities. To tackle this issue of lapse in awareness, this transverse case work carried out to evaluate the perceptions of mothers about the mental issues of their children in Jinnah Hospital, Lahore.

METHODOLOGY:

The participants of this case work were the mothers of children who appeared in OPD of pediatric ward the Jinnah Hospital, Lahore for some physical problem. We informed the purpose of the case work

to all the mothers due to some issues of confidentiality. Collection of the data carried out with the help of questionnaire. All the participants gave written consent to participate in the case work. There were total 2 sections in questionnaire. There was information about the demography as age, qualification etc. in the 1st section. There was a checklist in the in the 2nd section from this particular subject in which we asked from mothers to discover the signs or behaviors which are psycho-pathological according to their thinking, their knowledge about the mental disorders of children, their views about the treatment of these complications and what will they do to help the mentally ill child [3]. We also asked from mothers to give their suggestions to increase the knowledge of the mental issues of children in populations of our society. Interview carried out to fill the questionnaire due to the problem of illiteracy. SPSS V. 17 was in use for the statistical analysis of the collected information.

RESULTS:

There were 91 mothers who were willing to participate among one hundred and five approached. The single cause of their no participation was hurry to go back home or their child was uneasy in the environment of hospital. The average age of the participants was 32.80 ± 6.36 . Most of mothers 91.0% (n: 82) were housewives. Total 84.60% (n: 77) found with less than ten year of education & 82.40% (n: 75) females told that monthly oncome of their house was below twenty thousand rupees. How commonly different emotional, behavioral & cognitive manifestations were available in the perceptions of mother about the metal health issue of their children as elaborated in Table-1.

Table-I: Frequency of mothers perceiving various manifestations as mental health problems

Mental Health problems Manifestations	No	Percent	
Emotional & Cognitive Manifestations	Thinking of Suicide	60.0	65.90
	Phobias	58.0	63.70
	Hallucinations	56.0	61.50
	Stress	43.0	47.30
	School refusal	39.0	42.90
	Lack of attention	37.0	40.70
	Superstitions	32.0	35.20
	Somatic complaints	26.0	28.60
	Daytime wetting of clothes	16.0	17.60
Behavioral Manifestations	Anger	56.0	61.50
	Negative Thinking	52.0	57.10

Disobedience	47.0	51.60
Verbal abuse	46.0	50.50
Quarreling	44.0	48.40
Physical abuse of others	43.0	47.30
Lying	41.0	45.10
Fire setting	37.0	40.70
Sleep disorders	31.0	34.10
Escape from home	28.0	30.80
Drug use.	23.0	25.30
Truancy from school	21.0	23.10

We asked their opinions on reasons of the problems of mental illness of their child, most of females told many reasons as family problems, their social & economic condition, and some genetic reasons etc. as elaborated in Table-2.

Table-II: Mother's views regarding likely causes and preferred treatment for mental disorders.

Mothers Views		No	Percent
Causes of Mental Health Problems	Family problems	60.0	65.90
	Social problems	55.0	60.40
	Economic problems	54.0	59.30
	Genetic diseases	39.0	42.90
	Being possessed	33.0	36.30
	Organic brain lesions	27.0	29.70
	Others	8.0	8.80
Preferred type of treatment	Medication	70.0	76.90
	Recitation of Holy Quran	60.0	65.90
	Psychotherapy	52.0	57.10
	Taveez	14.0	15.40

Total 71 females were with the view to take their child to the psychiatrist in mental suffering of their children, 44.0% (n: 40) females will give priority to consult pediatrician, 27.50% (n: 25) will go to scholars of religion, 24.20% (n: 22) will go to general practitioner, 17.60% (n: 16) will consult to spiritual healer whereas 12.10% (n: 11) will take their child to the homeopathic specialist for these complications. Most of the females were available with belief on the treatment with medicines as available in Table-2. Total 50.50% (n: 44) mothers stated that TV programs were very helpful to provide awareness about the mental issues of their children public opinions, specialists views and leaflets were another source for the increase in the awareness among females with different ratios.

DISCUSSION:

This case work investigate the perceptions of mothers associated with the mental sickness of their children and facilities in Lahore city. Most of the mothers showed the manifestation as concluded by many other case works in different parts of the world [3]. But same stress on emotional & behavioral signs is in opposition with disparity reporting of the past case works about the perception of the parents [4, 5]. Amazingly, a small amount of our participants permitted somatic grievances as a probable signs of the mental illness of the children regardless the proofs displaying an important relationship between unsolved somatic signs & depression and anxiety among children of our country Pakistan [6].

Most of the probable reasonable aspects for the mental abnormalities of children according to mothers were family problems, economic and social condition. The emotional state of adolescents, issues in family & bad luck are some of the prompting factors for mental suffering [7]. A minority of very small size Karma was also the possible reason

according to one case work conducted in Australia [8]. In the same manner, the possession of spirit, God punishment, luck, impact of magic are some of the vital reasons for these mental abnormalities of Asia [9]. Trends of the priority of accessing the professionals of health care field & developed modalities of therapies rather than conventional ones is also available in many other case works [3, 8].

The most preferred interventions were getting treatment & medications in accordance with the perceptions of mothers for the mental illness of their children but sixty six percent females considered the Holy Quran's recitation as the most vital intervention. This was due to the dominance of the religion Islam in our culture prevailing in our country Pakistan. The perception of the parents for the advantages of the therapy has relation to the application and compliance of the health care facilities [10, 11]. There was less involvement of fathers for the prevention of health issues in their children. This was due to the impact of society and culture where mothers are more responsible for

household and children activities.

There are some limitations of this case work as very small size of samples and presentation was only confine to single one center. Fathers usually spend less time with their children therefore we collected the information from mothers only.

CONCLUSION:

Regardless of some limitations, this current case work highlighted very vital and poorly tacit area as understanding of mothers about reasons, sign and most proper interference for treatment in the mentally ill children. There is a need of further qualitative case works to get more awareness about the perception of parents to help them in providing service to their mentally ill children.

REFERENCES:

1. Syed E, Hussein SA, Mahmud S. Screening for emotional and behavioural problems amongst 5–11-year-old school children in Karachi, Pakistan. *Soc Psychiatry Psychiatric Epidemiol.* 2007;42(5):421-427.
2. Syed E, Hussein SA, Haidry SZ. Prevalence of emotional and behavioural problems among primary school children in Karachi, Pakistan — multi informant survey. *Indian J Pediatr.* 2009;76(6):623-627.
3. Thabet AA, Gammal HE, Vostanis P. Palestinian mothers' perceptions of child mental health problems and services. *World Psychiatry.* 2012;5(2):108-112.
4. Bengi-Arslan L, Verhulst F, Van der Ende J, Erol N. Understanding childhood (problem)behaviours from a cultural perspective: comparison of problem behaviours and competencies in Turkish immigrant, Turkish and Dutch children. *Soc Psychiatry Psychiatr Epidemiol.* 1997;32(8):477-484.
5. Yeh M, Hough R, McCabe K, Lau A, Garland A. Parental belief about the cause of child problems: exploring racial/ ethnic patterns. *J Am Acad Child Adolesc Psychiatry.* 2004;43(5):605-612.
6. Imran N, Ani C, Mahmood Z, Hassan KA, Bhatti MR. Anxiety and depression predicted by medically unexplained symptoms in Pakistani Children: A case-control study. *J Psychosom Res.* 2014;76(2):105-112. doi: 10.1016/j.jpsychores.2013.11.016
7. Imran N, Azeem W, Chaudhry MR, Butt Z. Illness perceptions in adolescents with a Psychiatric diagnosis in Pakistan. *Psychiatric Bulletin.* 2015;39(4):174-178.
8. McKelvey RS, Baldassar LV, Sang DL, Roberts L. Vietnamese parental perceptions of child and adolescent mental illness. *J Am Acad Child Adolesc Psychiatry.* 1999 ;38(10):1302-1309.
9. Alyahya F. Saudi Arabia: acknowledging problems in a transitional culture. In: Appleby L, Araya R (eds). *Mental health services in the global village.* London: Gaskell, 1991:99-108.
10. Sayal K, Taylor E, Beecham J. Parental perception of problems and mental health service use for hyperactivity. *J Am Acad Child Adolesc Psychiatry.* 2003;42(12):1410-1414.
11. Horwitz S, Demeter C, Hayden M, Storfer-Isser A, Frazier TW, Fristad MA. Parents' Perceptions of Benefit of Children's Mental Health Treatment and Continued Use of Services. *Psych Serv.* 2012;63(8):793–801. doi: 10.1176/appi.ps.201100460a